

Effect of micelle environment on the photochromism of 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole

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Abstract : Photochromism is a reversible structural change of distinguishing absorption features of a molecule upon irradiation with light. The effect of matrix environment on the quantitative parameters (rate, quantum yield, energy, entropy) of photochrome is noteworthy. In this work, the micelle environment is imposed on 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole in methanol solution using Triton-X-100, CTAB and SDS and the transformation of *E*-to-*Z* (*trans*-to-*cis*) configuration about -N=N- bond is studied. It is observed that the rate and quantum yields of photoisomerisation are enhanced when photochrome is embedded on neutral (Triton-X-100) and cation (CTAB) micelles while these are significantly decreased in anion micelle (SDS). The effect of micelle on the rate and quantum yields follow the sequence : Triton-X-100 > CTAB > no micelle > SDS. The *Z*-to-*E* (*cis*-to-*trans*) isomerisation proceeds slowly upon visible light irradiation while it is appreciably fast on increasing temperature. The activation energy (E_a) of *Z* (*cis*) \rightarrow *E* (*trans*) thermal isomerisation is amplified in presence of Triton-X-100 and CTAB while it is decreased by adding SDS. Thus, the lowering of *Z*-to-*E* thermal process in presence of neutral and cation micelle and increasing in SDS phase are supported.

Keywords : Photochromism, 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole, micelles, activation energy.

Introduction

Light is used an efficient nondestructive trigger for external control of molecular switches and has massive advantages over other activation process like thermal, magnetic, mechanical, electrical, redox procedures. The process has been known for nine decades¹⁻³ but recently been found enormous applications for controlling the properties of functional polymeric materials⁴, useful for the photo-control of biomolecules⁵ and for novel applications such as data storage^{6,7} and self-assembling systems^{8,9}.

For the last few years we have been examined the *E*-to-*Z* (*trans*-to-*cis*) isomerisation of arylazoimidazole (Scheme 1) and their metal complexes¹⁰⁻¹⁷. It is a reversible photo-induced transformation between two molecular states whose absorption spectra are significantly different. Different physical and chemical parameters such as change of solvent polarities, presence of noninteracting (innocent) and interacting (noninnocent) foreign molecules

affect the photoisomerisation¹⁸ rate and quantum yields. Using metal complexes of different oxidation state, electronic configuration of metal ions, different ancillary ligands steric crowding, electron donating and withdrawing groups etc. control photoisomerisation process. In this work, the effect of micelle (neutral and ionic) in solution on the photoisomerisation of 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole has been examined. Formation of hydrophobic core may increase concentration of organic molecules which certainly change physicochemical properties of the concerned system. Herein, we use SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100 in methanol medium for the examination of photochromism of four different 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole.

Results and discussion

1-Methyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thiomethyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole (SMeaiNMe) (**1a**), 1-ethyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thiomethyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole (SEtaiNMe) (**1b**), 1-methyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thio-$

ethylphenylazo}imidazole (SMeaaiNMe) (**2a**) and 1-ethyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioethyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole (SEtaaiNMe) (**2b**) and three different micelles, Triton-X-100 (nonionic), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, cationic) and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, anionic) were used in this work (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Ligands and micelles used in this work.

The photochromism :

The absorption spectra are recorded in methanol solution in 200–900 nm. The spectra of the compounds show a structured absorption band around 370–390 nm with a molar absorption coefficient on the order of $10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions, and a tail extending into 450 nm, a $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transition¹⁰. Irradiation of UV light to methanol solution of SRaaiNR' changes the absorption spectrum as shown in Fig. 1. The intense peak at λ_{max} decreases, which is accompanied by increase of longer absorption band of the spectrum until a stationary state is reached (Photostationary state-I, PS-I). Subsequent irradiation at the newly appeared longer wavelength peak reverses the course of the reaction and the original spectrum is recovered up to a point, which is another Photostationary state-II (PS-II) under irradiation at the longer wavelength peak. The quantum yields of the *E*-to-*Z* (*trans*-to-*cis*) photoisomerization were determined using those of azobenzene as a standard and the results are given in Table 1.

It is observed that upon irradiation with UV light *E*-to-*Z* photoisomerisation has proceeded and the *Z* molar ratio is reached to >95%. The absorption spectra of the *E*-ligands changed with isosbestic points upon excitation (Figs. 2–4) into the *Z*-isomer. The UV light is irradiated to 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole in methanol in

Fig. 1. Spectral changes of SMeaaiNMe upon repeated irradiation at 357 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C in methanol solution.

presence of micelle (concentration higher than CMC) and the rate of photoisomerisation changes are recorded in Table 1. Micelles greatly affect the ground and excited state of the photoactive molecules¹⁹. Aggregation of micelle generates organized system above critical micelle

Table 1. Excitation wavelength (λ_{π, π^*}), rate of *E* (*trans*) \rightarrow *Z* (*cis*) conversion and quantum yield ($\Phi_{E \rightarrow Z}$) of photoisomerisation in presence of different micelle

Compounds	Micelle	Excitation wavelength (nm)	Isosbestic (nm)	Rate of <i>E</i> \rightarrow <i>Z</i> conversion $\times 10^8$ (s ⁻¹)	Quantum yield <i>E</i> -to- <i>Z</i>
SMeaaiNMe (1a) ^a	Non-micelle	357	337	4.908	0.317
SMeaaiNEt (1b) ^a		358	337	3.108	0.232
SEtaaiNMe (2a) ^a		357	336	4.670	0.290
SEtaaiNEt (2b) ^a		356	335	2.950	0.197
SMeaaiNMe (1a)	Cationic (CTAB)	355	333, 500	6.456	0.412
SMeaaiNEt (1b)		356	332, 502	5.108	0.321
SEtaaiNMe (2a)		355	330, 503	5.212	0.342
SEtaaiNEt (2b)		357	333, 500	3.961	0.256
SMeaaiNMe (1a)	Nonionic (TX-100)	355	332, 497	6.767	0.448
SMeaaiNEt (1b)		356	331, 499	5.324	0.356
SEtaaiNMe (2a)		356	335, 501	5.764	0.391
SEtaaiNEt (2b)		358	332, 500	4.521	0.285
SMeaaiNMe (1a)	Anionic (SDS)	356	333, 503	3.831	0.248
SMeaaiNEt (1b)		357	331, 504	2.964	0.194
SEtaaiNMe (2a)		356	333, 503	3.521	0.218
SEtaaiNEt (2b)		355	332, 501	2.015	0.148

^aData collected from Ref. 27.**Fig. 3.** Spectral changes of SMeaaiNMe in presence of Triton-X-100 in methanol-water (1 : 30 v/v) mixture upon repeated irradiation at 355 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C.

concentration (CMC). Micelle can catalyze many reactions due to the “concentration effect” in the micelle pseudo-phase and also alter the reaction pathways. In the present study cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), Triton-X-100 and sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) micelles have been selected as representative of positive, neutral and negative surfaces, respectively. The π - π^* transition

of photochrome has been shifted to longer wavelength ($\Delta\lambda = 7$ –20 nm) in micelle phase compared to free ligand state. The results in Table 1 show that the neutral (Triton-X-100) and cationic micelles (CTAB) enhance the rate of *E*-to-*Z* isomerisation by 13–71% while anion micelle (SDS) reduces the photoisomerisation rate by 5–32% with reference to the free ligand data (Table 1). The sensitivity of quantum yields (Φ) of photoisomerisation also increases

Fig. 4. Spectral changes of SMeaiNMe in presence of SDS in methanol-water (1 : 10 v/v) mixture upon repeated irradiation at 356 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C.

in CTAB (18–38%) and Triton-X-100 (35–53%) and shows decrement in SDS phase (16–25%). The results imply that *Z* configuration in micelle phase is more stable than free ligand phase with respect to light irradiation^{20–22}. Effect of micelle microenvironment on photoisomerisation of a series of small molecular weight arylazoimidazoles has been examined²³ and also supports present observation. The rate and quantum yields (Φ) of photoisomerisation of SRaaiNR', in this work, follows the sequence : Triton-X-100 > CTAB > no micelle > SDS. It is assumed that the confined spaces of micelle²⁴ may accommodate the photochrome and surface concentration could be enhanced. The property of analyte in the micelle phase depends on space in the cavity, flexibility of the boundary and the persistent interactions that hold the photochrome within the cavity. Free space surrounding the photochrome within a confined cage of micelle has changed and plays a vital role in controlling the motional performance of the species²⁵. Various weak interactions between the photochrome and micelle functions such as hydrophobic, van der Waals and C–H... π are important in the context of the photoreaction of the molecules. Thus compartment size, polarity, reactive centres are responsible to regulate the extent of *E*-to-*Z* isomerisation under UV-irradiation. Micelle probe is hydrophobic and reduces the noncovalent (C–H... π , π ... π) interactions which leads to stabilize the entrapped photochrome²⁶. It may be the reason for increased rate of *E*-to-*Z* photoisomerisation in neutral (Triton-X-100) and cationic (CTAB) micelles than that of free ligand (Table

1). Anion micelle (SDS) may destabilize the *cis*-structure because of strong dipolar interaction than that of *E* structure since higher dipole moment of earlier one. This may be the reason for lowering of the rate of photoisomerisation.

The quantum yields have been measured for the *E*-to-*Z* ($\Phi_{E \rightarrow Z}$) photoisomerisation of these compounds in methanol on irradiation of UV wavelength (Table 1). The $\Phi_{E \rightarrow Z}$ values are significantly dependent on nature of substituents. The Et substituent at thiol group (S-Me to S-Et) and Et substituent at N(1)-position (1-Me to 1-Et) both reduce $\Phi_{E \rightarrow Z}$ values. In general, increase in mass of the molecule reduces the rate of isomerisation, *E*-to-*Z* (Table 1).

Irradiation of UV light from photo-source of wavelength 370 nm to the solution of 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole, in methanol has transformed *E*→*Z* isomer (>95%). Further irradiation using visible light source at 455 nm has initiated transference of *Z*→*E* isomer. However, the process is very slow. While the thermal change at dark is relatively fast (Fig. 5) and the reaction rate is characterized by a single exponential function. The unimolecular rate constant of the thermal backward isomerisation (k) was obtained by the analysis of the measured absorbance, $\text{Abs}(t) = (\text{Abs}_t - \text{Abs}_c)e^{-kt} + \text{Abs}_c$, where Abs_c and Abs_t are absorbances corresponding to pure samples of *c* (*cis*) and *t* (*trans*) forms, respectively. The thermal *Z*-to-*E* isomerisation rates have been calculated by monitoring absorption changes intermittently for a *Z*-rich solution kept in the dark at constant temperature (T) in the range 298–313 K. The activation energy (E_a) and the frequency factor (A) were obtained from $\ln k = \ln A - E_a/RT$, where k is the measured rate constant, R is the gas constant, and T is temperature. The values of the activation free energy (ΔG^*) and the activation entropy (ΔS^*) were obtained through the relationships,

$$\Delta G^* = E_a - RT - T\Delta S^* \text{ and}$$

$$\Delta S^* = [\ln A - 1 - \ln(k_B T/h)/R]$$

where k_B and h are Boltzmann's and Planck's constants, respectively.

The activation energy, E_a , of thermal isomerisation has been calculated by fitting the temperature dependent k values (Fig. 6) and the results are listed in Table 2. Data reveal that the activation energy (E_a) increases in the micelle phase and the thermal *Z*-to-*E* isomerisation rate of

Fig. 5. The thermal spectral changes of SMEaaiNMe in methanol in presence of CTAB at 30 °C. Inset figure shows spectra of *Z*- and *E*-isomer of SMEaaiNMe.

Fig. 6. The Eyring plots of rate constants of *Z*-to-*E* thermal isomerisation of (a) SMEaaiNMe in presence of Triton-X-100; (b) SMEaaiNMe in presence of CTAB; (c) SMEaaiNMe and (d) SMEaaiNMe in presence of SDS at different temperatures.

the ligands are decreased by 20–40% irrespective of nature of micelles. *Z*-isomer is more polar than *E*-isomer and hence former is better stabilized in micelle phase. This is also supported by thermal data in Table 2.

Experimental

1-Alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles were synthesized by reported procedure²⁸. Imidazole, aniline, *p*-toluidine were of analytical reagent grade collected from SRL, India. SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate), cetyl(trimethyl)ammonium bromide (CTAB) and Triton-X-100 were collected from Sigma-Aldrich. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade as received. UV-Vis spectral data were obtained using Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 spectrophotometer and photoexcitation has been carried out using Perkin-Elmer LS-55 spectrofluorimeter.

Table 2. Rate and activation parameters for *Z* (*cis*) → *E* (*trans*) thermal isomerisation

Compd.	Micelle	Temp. (K)	Rate of thermal <i>Z</i> → <i>E</i> conversion × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	<i>E</i> _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>H</i> * (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> * (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Δ <i>G</i> * (kJ mol ⁻¹)
1a^a	Non-micelle	298	4.329	25.42	22.88	-232.41	93.87
		303	5.295				
		308	6.191				
		313	7.091				
1b^a		298	4.614	22.99	20.45	-240.02	93.77
		303	5.598				
		308	6.293				
		313	7.269				
2a^a		298	4.425	21.92	19.38	-244.04	93.94
		303	5.123				
		308	5.985				

Table-2 (contd.)

		313	6.279				
2b^a		298	4.625	18.88	16.34	-253.96	93.93
		303	5.123				
		308	5.985				
		313	6.589				
1a	CTAB	298	3.294	31.28	28.74	-214.92	94.40
		303	4.255				
		308	5.211				
		313	6.024				
1b		298	3.501	28.79	26.25	-222.85	94.33
		303	4.329				
		308	5.394				
		313	6.034				
2a		298	3.689	26.90	24.36	-228.76	94.25
		303	4.498				
		308	5.532				
		313	6.132				
2b		298	3.909	23.71	21.17	-238.97	94.18
		303	4.695				
		308	5.541				
		313	6.153				
1a	Triton-X-100	298	2.651	36.09	33.59	-200.73	94.92
		303	3.312				
		308	4.122				
		313	5.361				
1b		298	2.806	32.23	29.68	-213.01	94.76
		303	3.821				
		308	4.316				
		313	5.381				
2a		298	2.924	30.15	27.61	-219.61	94.71
		303	3.967				
		308	4.339				
		313	5.421				
2b		298	3.109	28.17	25.64	-225.85	94.64
		303	3.999				
		308	4.434				
		313	5.502				
1a	SDS	298	5.414	19.63	17.09	-249.85	93.38
		303	6.615				
		308	7.213				
		313	8.013				
1b		298	5.539	18.28	15.74	-254.12	93.38
		303	6.899				
		308	7.233				
		313	8.067				
2a		298	5.831	16.98	14.45	-258.17	93.32

	303	6.904				
	308	7.321				
	313	8.234				
2b	298	5.991	15.74	13.20	-262.19	93.31
	303	6.909				
	308	7.335				
	313	8.235				

^aData collected from Ref. 27.

Scheme 2. Model photochromism of SRaaNR' embedded in micelle.

Photometric measurements :

Absorption spectra were taken with a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 UV/Vis spectrophotometer in a 1 × 1 cm quartz optical cell maintained at 25 °C. The light source of a Perkin-Elmer LS 55 spectrofluorimeter was used as an excitation light, with a slit width of 10 nm. An optical filter was used to cut off overtones when necessary. The absorption spectra of the *cis* isomers were obtained by extrapolation of the absorption spectra of a *cis*-rich mixture for which the composition is known from ¹H NMR integration. Quantum yields (ϕ) were obtained by measuring initial *trans*-to-*cis* isomerisation rates (ν) in a well-stirred solution within the above instrument using the equation,

$$\nu = (\phi I_0/V)(1 - 10^{-Abs})$$

where I_0 is the photon flux at the front of the cell, V is the volume of the solution, and Abs is the initial absorbance at the azobenzene ($\phi = 0.11$) for $\pi-\pi^*$ excitation²⁹ under the same irradiation condition.

Conclusion

1-Alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole isomerizes from stable *E*- to *Z*-isomer on light irradiation at the UV

wavelength. The reverse, *Z*-to-*E*, is very slow by light and susceptible to heat. The isomerisation is dependent on the composition of the photochrome and its physical environment. In this work, the micelle environment controls the photoisomerisation of 1-alkyl-2- $\{(o\text{-thioalkyl})\text{phenylazo}\}$ imidazole in methanol solution using Triton-X-100, CTAB and SDS. The effect of micelle on the rate and quantum yields follow the sequence : Triton-X-100 > CTAB > no micelle > SDS. Variable temperature *Z*-to-*E* (*cis*-to-*trans*) isomerisation determines the activation energy (E_a) of *Z* (*cis*) \rightarrow *E* (*trans*) and also follow that the same sequence.

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References

1. G. S. Hartley, *Nature*, 1937, **140**, 281.
2. H. Durr and H. Bouas-Laurent (Eds), "Photochromism : Molecules and Systems", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2003.
3. B. Feringa, "Molecular Switches", Wiley-VCH, 2001.
4. M. Irie, Y. Hirano, S. Hashimoto and K. Hayashi, *Macromolecules*, 1981, **14**, 262.
5. A. A. Beharry and G. A. Woolley, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 4422.
6. M. Kamenjicki, I. K. Lednev and S. A. Asher, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2004, **108**, 12637.
7. A. Archut, F. Vogtle, L. De Cola, G. C. Azzellini, V. Balzani, P. S. Ramanujam and R. H. Berg, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 1998, **4**, 699.
8. H. Sawada, T. Tsuzuki-ishi, T. Kijima, J. Kawakami, M.

- Iizuka and M. Yoshida, *J. Colloid. Interf. Sci.*, 2011, **359**, 461.
9. B. V. Shankar and A. Patnaik, *Langmuir*, 2006, **22**, 4758.
10. J. Otsuki, K. Suwa, K. Narutaki, C. Sinha, I. Yoshikawa and K. Araki, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2005, **109**, 8064.
11. J. Otsuki, K. Suwa, K. K. Sarker and C. Sinha, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2007, **111**, 1403.
12. K. K. Sarker, S. Saha Halder, D. Banerjee, T. K. Mondal, A. R. Paital, P. K. Nanda, P. Raghavaiah and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 2955.
13. K. K. Sarker, D. Sardar, K. Suwa, J. Otsuki and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 8291.
14. K. K. Sarker, B. G. Chand, K. Suwa, J. Cheng, T.-H. Lu, J. Otsuki and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 670.
15. P. Pratihari, T. K. Mondal, A. K. Patra and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2009, **48**, 2760.
16. G. Saha, P. Datta, K. K. Sarker, R. Saha, G. Mostafa and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2011, **30**, 614.
17. D. Mallick, A. Nandi, S. Datta, K. K. Sarker, T. Kr. Mondal and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2012, **31**, 506.
18. T. Schultz, J. Quenneville, B. Levine, A. Toniolo, T. J. Martínez, S. Lochbrunner, M. Schmitt, J. P. Shaffer, M. Z. Zgierski and A. Stolow, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 8098.
19. F. Serra and E. M. Terentjev, *Macromolecules*, 2008, **41**, 981.
20. M. Ziótek and A. E. Izabela Sobczak, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 2009, **63**, 211.
21. J. C. Crano and R. J. Guglielmetti, "Organic Photochromic and Thermochromic Compounds : Physicochemical studies", Springer, 1999.
22. J. De Kok, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1985, **42**, 663.
23. P. Gayen, K. K. Sarker and C. Sinha, *Colloids and Surfaces A : Physicochem. Eng. Aspects*, 2013, **429**, 60.
24. J. Mata, J. Patel, N. Jain, G. Ghosh and P. Bahadur, *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.*, 2006, **297**, 797.
25. A. Parthasarathy and V. Ramamurthy, *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.*, 2011, **10**, 1455.
26. H. Sakai, H. Ebana, K. Sakai, K. Tsuchiya, T. Ohkubo and M. Abe, *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.*, 2007, **316**, 1027.
27. K. K. Sarker, S. Saha Halder, D. Banerjee, T. K. Mondal, A. R. Paital, P. K. Nanda, P. Raghavaiah and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 2955.
28. S. Saha (Halder), S. Roy, T. K. Mondal, R. Saha and C. Sinha, *Z. Anorg. Alleg. Chem.*, 2013, **639**, 1861.
29. G. Zimmerman, L. Chow and U. Paik, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3528.